

CONDUCTING AN EXPERIMENT ON SOLAR PANELS BASED ON AN AUTONOMOUS PHOTOVOLTAIC MODULE

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Abstract. *In this article, we have simulated the generation of a solar panel using a control power supply block in Simulink software. To generate the required power and voltage, solar panels are connected in series. We used a special algorithm, IRF-540 MOSFET and several Simulink blocks to model the off-grid system in the Simulink program. In the context of renewable energy systems such as solar or wind energy, we have created a model of an off-grid system. Off-grid is a system that operates independently of the electrical grid. In the off-grid system, the current and voltage during the charging process of the battery, as well as the charging percentage are analyzed through graphs, and it can be observed that the voltage is constant at 12V during the charging process, and the current changes indirectly.*

Keywords: *Simulink software, generation, special algorithm, off-grid system, charging percentage, charging process.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada biz Simulink dasturiy ta'minotida boshqaruv quvvat bloki yordamida quyosh panelini yaratishni simulyatsiya qildik. Kerakli quvvat va kuchlanishni ishlab chiqarish uchun quyosh panellari ketma-ket ulanadi. Simulink dasturida tarmoqdan tashqari tizimni modellashtirish uchun maxsus algoritmi, IRF-540 MOSFET va bir nechta Simulink bloklaridan foydalandik. Quyosh yoki shamol energiyasi kabi qayta tiklanadigan energiya tizimlari kontekstida biz tarmoqdan tashqari tizim modelini yaratdik. Off-grid - bu elektr tarmog'idan mustaqil ravishda ishlaydigan tizim. Tarmoqdan tashqari tizimda akkumulyatorni zaryadlash jarayonida oqim va kuchlanish, shuningdek, zaryadlanish foizi grafiklar orqali tahlil qilinadi va zaryadlash jarayonida kuchlanish 12V da doimiy bo'lib, oqim bilvosita o'zgarishini kuzatish mumkin.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Simulink dasturi, avlod, maxsus algoritmi, tarmoqdan tashqari tizim, zaryadlash foizi, zaryadlash jarayoni.*

Аннотация. *В этой статье мы смоделировали генерацию солнечной панели с использованием блока управления питанием в программном обеспечении Simulink. Для генерации необходимой мощности и напряжения солнечные панели подключаются последовательно. Мы использовали специальный алгоритм, IRF-540 MOSFET и несколько блоков Simulink для моделирования автономной системы в программе Simulink. В контексте систем возобновляемой энергии, таких как солнечная или ветровая энергия, мы создали модель автономной системы. Автономная система — это система, которая работает независимо от электрической сети. В автономной системе ток и напряжение во время процесса зарядки аккумулятора, а также процент зарядки анализируются с помощью графиков, и можно заметить, что напряжение постоянно на уровне 12 В во время процесса зарядки, а ток изменяется косвенно.*

Ключевые слова: программное обеспечение Simulink, генерация, специальный алгоритм, автономная система, процент зарядки, процесс зарядки.

INTRODUCTION

The demand for electricity is increasing year by year. Several factors such as population growth, urbanization levels, and increasing demand for home appliances are increasing the demand for electricity. In addition, the limited amount of resources increases the demand for renewable energy. In particular, the solar energy system is causing the expansion of the scale of its use. At the same time, solar panels are entering every home. Several works are being carried out to achieve its targeted use and high efficiency. We also investigated the modeling of off-grid system of solar panels in this paper [1]. An off-grid system is a system that can operate independently without a local network and has several advantages and disadvantages. Its advantages are that it can work independently, can collect excess charge, and can be used in places where the power grid does not reach, but its disadvantages are that it does not provide the necessary amount of electricity on cloudy days [2]. In addition, there are losses in the system itself, in the conversion and charging processes. Optimizing them as much as possible will help increase the demand on the system [3].

PART OF THE RESEARCH

Connecting the panels in series to produce the required power and voltage.

This figure shows a model of connecting solar panels in series. When we connected 10 of our 200-Watt panels in series we got a 2kW power supply. We can see that the value of our current is 7.5 Amps and the voltage is 265 Volts [4-6].

Fig. 1. Series connection model of solar panels

EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES

Controller selection and parameter calculation

Values we know:

$$U_k = 265 \text{ V} - \text{Input voltage};$$

$$U_{ch} = 12 \text{ V} - \text{Output voltage};$$

$P_0 = 2000 \text{ W}$ – Maximum power
 $\nu_{km} = 5 \text{ kHz}$ – Switching frequency;
 $U_r = 0.12 \text{ V}$ – Pulsation voltage;
 $I_r = 16.67 \text{ A}$ - Pulsation current.

Calculations:

$$L = \frac{U_{ch}(U_k - U_{ch})}{I_r * \nu_{km} * U_k} = \frac{12 * (265 - 12)}{16.67 * 5000 * 265} = 0.14 \text{ mH} - \text{Inductance} \quad (1)$$

$$C = \frac{I_r}{8 * \nu_{km} * U_r} = \frac{16.67}{8 * 5000 * 0.12} = 3.47 \text{ mF} - \text{capacitor capacity} \quad (2)$$

A model of an off-grid system

Off-grid refers to a system or lifestyle that operates independently of the electrical grid. In an off-grid system, electricity is generated and consumed on-site without relying on utility power. Off-grid systems are typically used in remote areas where grid connectivity is not feasible or cost-effective [3]. They usually rely on renewable energy sources such as solar panels, wind turbines or hydropower to generate electricity [7-9]. Energy storage systems such as batteries or fuel cells are used to store excess energy for use during periods when a renewable energy source is not producing electricity, such as at night or in low sunlight conditions [10].

Fig. 2. Simulink model of off-grid system

A metal oxide semiconductor field effect transistor (MOSFET) is a semiconductor device that is controlled by a gate signal ($\gamma > 0$). The MOSFET device is connected in parallel with an internal diode that is reverse-biased ($V_{ds} < 0$) and turns on when no gate signal is applied ($g = 0$). The model is simulated with an ideal switch controlled by a logic signal ($g > 0$ or $g = 0$), with a diode connected in parallel [11-12].

A MOSFET device turns on when a positive signal is applied to the gate input ($g > 0$), regardless of whether the drain-source voltage is positive or negative. If no signal is applied to the gate input ($g = 0$), the internal diode will only conduct when the voltage exceeds its forward voltage V_f .

Main Results of the Work

Graphical analysis of the off-grid system

Fig. 3. Charging schedule

This graph is a graph of the current and voltage and the charging percentage of the battery charging process in the offgrid system [7]. During the charging process, it can be observed that the voltage is a constant 12V and the current changes directly over time [8, 12].

Fig. 4. Graph of the current during the charging process

In this graph, we can see that the graph of the current when charging the battery has a saw-tooth shape.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can say that each system has its advantages and disadvantages in the use of solar panels. If we take the on-grid system in particular, the advantage of this system is that it can work directly with an external source during the production of electricity or there is a possibility of transferring excess energy to an external source. This causes the consumption of external sources to be much easier from the economic side. Disadvantages are the inability to work independently. In addition, we can see that the correct conduct of the charging process in the off-grid system directly depends on the correct selection of the MOSFET. The advantage of this system is that it can work independently.

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